

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERACTIVE AND ACTION GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRESCHOOLERS.

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Annotation: This article discusses the importance of using games in teaching English. Games make classes interesting and exciting. They help improve the vocabulary of the language of students. Also games develop memory, ability, resourcefulness. The article substantiates the role of games in teaching English. Teaching lessons through activities requires convenient storage and easy retrieval of materials, objects, pictures, toys, games, conversation pieces and other props. The article provides several examples of games for use in English lessons. Using these interactive methods in English lessons more useful and meaningful. If you use active games aimed at developing students' thinking in the lessons, then you can achieve the goal set in the lesson. Through playing games pupils can learn the English the way children learn their mother tongue, without being aware they are studying, thus without stress, they can learn a lot, even sky pupils can participate positively. They can express their own opinions easily helping of these methods.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается важность использования игр в обучении английскому языку. Игры делают занятия интересными и увлекательными. Они помогают улучшить словарный запас языка учащихся. Также игры развивают память, способности, находчивость. В статье обосновывается роль игр в обучении английскому языку. Преподавание уроков через деятельность требует удобного хранения и легкого поиска материалов, предметов, картинок, игрушек, игр, предметов для разговоров и другого реквизита. В статье приведены несколько примеров игр для использования на уроках английского языка. Использование этих интерактивных методов на уроках английского языка более полезно и содержательно. Если использовать на уроках подвижные игры, направленные на развитие мышления учащихся, то можно добиться поставленной на уроке цели. С помощью игр ученики могут изучать английский язык так же, как дети изучают свой родной язык, не осознавая, что они учатся, таким образом, без стресса, они могут многому научиться, даже школьники могут принять

положительное участие. Они могут легко выражать свое мнение с помощью этих методов.

Key words: Teaching foreign language, interactive methods, communicating skills, different games, learner's vocabulary, teaching materials, vocabulary, structure explanations and drills, native language, pedagogical value.

Introduction One of the important tasks of modern foreign language teaching methodology is to shape education for preschool children of different ages using these games. E.I. such as famous Methodists. Passov, M.N. Skatkin. "It's important to be accountable to yourself," M.N. "This game is supposed to promote a summary of what didactic questions, which psychic currents are designed to develop," Skatkin notes. "The game is just a surface layer, the configuration, its subject should be teaching, mastering the types of verbal activities" E.I. Passov provides information about the following features of play activities as a means of learning: accuracy, lack of coercion; individualized, highly individualized activity; teaching and learning in groups and through groups; formation of mental goals and abilities. D.B. Elkonin provides the game with four main goals for the preschool educator: a method of shaping the area of motivational need; way of knowing; a method of developing mental effects; a method of shaping voluntary action. The game defines the necessary disorders and education of the latest qualities personality; in this game, preschoolers learn behavioral settings, play, teach, change, nurture.

Research on the topic and their analysis The main factor of teaching foreign language is to improve the role of interactive methods. Because it makes the learners to motivate and keep their interests whole lessons. Interactive methods include games, songs, poems, activities. The game defines the necessary disorders and education of the latest qualities personality; in this game, preschoolers learn behavioral settings, play, teach, change, nurture. E.I. Passov emphasizes the following objectives of using the game in the learning process: to develop some skills; formation of defined speech skills; teaching communication skills; development of necessary abilities and mental functions; assimilating the context of speech. The language learning process requires one-third of the game techniques that combine and integrate other activities. Game methodology is based on creating an imaginary situation and assuming a specific role by a child or teacher. Learning games are divided into: situational, competitive, rhythmic-musical and artistic. Situational play involves role-playing games that mimic communication situations in a particular situation. Role-playing is a play activity in which children play different roles in life situations, for example: seller-buyer, doctor-patient, actor

and his fan, and so on. It's very important to monitor the process of mastering the amount of learning material by all children, and both partial and final control over young children is carried out in a playful way and assessment activities are not carried out. Play activities affect the formation of attention, memory, thinking, imagination, absolutely all cognitive processes. Thus, in particular, "the pedagogical and didactic significance of the business game is that it allows its participants to express themselves, learn to take an active position, and understand their professional ability". The ability to rely on play activities allows you to provide a natural motivation for speaking in a foreign language, making even the simplest sentences interesting and meaningful. Playing in foreign language teaching does not oppose educational activity, but is organically related to it. The following rules should be followed when choosing or inventing a game to be added to the lesson:

Before starting the game, answer the following questions: What is the purpose of the game, what should the child learn from it? What speech movement should he perform? Does the child know how to compose such a statement, are there any additional difficulties? After answering these questions, try to become a child yourself and come up with an interesting situation in which a statement on such a model can emerge. Think about how to describe this situation in a way that the child will immediately accept ... Enjoy playing with your child yourself!

The game has to be educational and it has to be a game. The Soviet encyclopedic dictionary defines play as an inefficient type of activity, the motive of which is not its result, but the process itself. This is a very important sign. Therefore, the introduction of the game into the classroom, its didactic outcome is important for the teacher, but can not be an incentive for children's activities. Consequently, play should change the style of relationship between children and the adult teacher who cannot force anything: the child can play only when he wants and is interested in her and sympathizes with her. A teacher can't just be a game organizer - he has to play with a child because children play with adults with great pleasure and the play environment is disrupted under the watchful eye of an outside observer. Games and problem solving activities, which are task-based and have a purpose beyond the production of correct speech, are the examples of the most preferable communicative activities. Such activities highlight not only the competence but only but also the performance of the learners. Both games and problem solving activities have a goal. Games are organized according to the rules and they are funny. Most games require choral responses or group works, problem solving activities, require individual response and creative solutions. Games and problem solving activities are generally used after the presentation, in the practice

part, because such communication – five tasks can only be handled after mastering sufficient grammar and lexical points. Through well-planned games, learners can practice and internalize vocabulary, grammar and structure extensively. By regarding the proficiency, age and experience of the learners, appropriate activities might be applied successfully. In sum, games and problem solving activities provide favorable usages for extended communicative practice of grammar. They are both motivating and challenging. They encourage the learners to interact and communicative. So, these activities create a meaningful context for language use. The use of such activities both increase the cooperation and in the classroom. So far, the usage of the songs, poems, games and problem solving 163 activities are clarified. The advantages and some key points are explained. It is now more apparent that the teaching of grammar can be supported effectively, by using such resources”. Such activities are pupil’s centered, hence by using them you give a chance to your pupils to express themselves, enjoy themselves during learning and the use the reserves of their minds.

Conclusion The results of research methods is the action games are a methodological unit focused on the proximal developmental zone, which combines a pedagogical goal with an attractive motive for the child.

Generally, young learners could not always concentrate and pay attention during the teaching-learning process. Were the lesson boring, they would play and chat with their friend. It could disturb the learning process and could make the class to be ineffective. By using game in teaching- learning process, the students were very enthusiastic in joining the activity. Therefore, the writer could handle the class because the students give more attention to the lesson. Games are enjoyable activity. Games can make the students to be more active in class. They will give more attention and will be active to response what the teacher teaches. Therefore, the students will accept the lesson easily.

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